

TWITTER DATASET FOR ADVANCED HATE SPEECH IDENTIFICATION

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Abstract: Individuals from various educational backgrounds and cultural backgrounds exchange their opinions on various parts of life on a daily basis thanks to the rapid development in microblogging services like Twitter, which provide indirect and trustworthy contact between individuals. People are at odds with each other due to the outcome of this. The dissemination of hate speech thereby turns into a very significant issue. It takes a lot of time and effort to manually identify such information on these websites. The use of derogatory, harsh, or hostile language towards a certain group of people who share a common property—be it gender, ethnicity, beliefs, or region—is known as hate speech. The suggested approach has the ability to automatically identify hate speech on Twitter. This strategy is founded on the TFIDF method and a bag of words. Classifiers for machine learning are trained using these attributes. After extensive testing on an existing Twitter dataset, the logistic regression classifier was able to identify whether or not a given message was hateful with an accuracy of 93.11%.

Keywords: Hate Speech, Dataset, Twitter

Introduction

Twitter is among the most widely used micro blogging platforms for communication. As per the official website, Twitter boasts of over 348 million members worldwide. 350000 tweets were created in a second on Twitter. Diverse cultural and educational backgrounds share their opinions on daily topics such as politics, movies, products, and other aspects of life. Many businesses and organizations are interested in this kind of information to find out what people think about films, goods, and political events. However, disagreements over opinions can occasionally cause communication between people to degenerate into harsh language. Such speech can take many other forms, including bullying, which is one of the main causes of suicide. Hate speech has real-world consequences in addition to its effects on the internet. Numerous innocent persons perished in mob lynching instances every year. Due to the laborious and time-consuming nature of manually identifying hate speech content on these kinds of websites, a model that can identify it automatically has been developed. There must be an immediate end to the usage and dissemination of such terminology. "Any speech that attacks a person or group on the basis of attributes such as race, religion, and ethnic origin, gender, disability, or gender identity" is classified as hate speech. The capacity of a system to learn on its own without explicit programming is known as machine learning. The system is trained using a variety of machine learning methods so that it may learn on its own and get better over time. The field of artificial intelligence known as natural language processing makes it possible for a computer system to comprehend human natural language. However, robots have a very hard time comprehending emotions. Sentiment analysis is the method used to determine if a language is expressing positive, negative, or neutral feelings. Natural language processing is used in sentiment analysis to determine the polarity of a given phrase.

In this research, we used natural language processing in Python to build a model for machine learning that can categorise a tweet that either hate speech or non-hate speech. We were able to extract the TFIDF characteristics and the bag of words using a publicly available Twitter dataset. These features were then used to train a logistic regression classifier, and the findings indicate that the classifier can identify hostile tweets with an accuracy of 93.11%.

Related Work

Opinion mining and sentiment analysis have drawn the attention of several scholars due to the rise in popularity of microblogging websites. The categorization of tweets is a topic covered in several recent studies. A range of machine learning approaches have been used to address hate speech material. Suggested a method that ranks the N-gram features based on their TFIDF values once they are extracted from the tweets. The machine learning algorithm uses these attributes to automatically classify tweets into three categories: inflammatory, hateful, and clean. Tweets are first translated into lower case before any extraneous information, such as stop words, URLs, space patterns, and Twitter mentions, is eliminated. Following data processing, a grid search is used to train three Logistic regressions, Naïve Bayes, and SVM are examples of machine learning classifiers. These classifiers are used to identify all possible combinations of the feature parameter. Test data were subjected to Cross-validation 10 times, and the outcome demonstrates that statistical analysis. This article also suggested the similar strategy, except instead of utilising Twitter API to gather tweets with hate speech keywords; the authors collected them using a crowdsourced hate speech definition. These PoS tags are created to record syntactic feature information after data processing operations such as stemming, ngrams, and TFIDF. Decision trees, Random Forest, Linear SVM, Naïve Bayes, and Logistic Regression are the five machine learning classifiers that are prepared and evaluated using Five-fold cross-validation. As compared to other classifiers, the results demonstrate that SVM and logistic regression work well. Introduced a method for gathering Twitter corpus of objective, negative, and positive attitudes automatically. Next, stop words are eliminated by tokenization once these corpora's n-grams and PoS tags have been extracted. Two procedures have been presented for the extraction of n-gram features. The first strategy computes the probability distribution's entropy for every data occurrence. The n-grams with low entropy were retained, whereas the n-grams with high entropy were eliminated. It is called salience, the second tactic. Sequences with high salience were retained. In terms of model construction accuracy, bigrams offer superior performance than salience. Once this is done, tweets are categorised into three groups using a multinomial naïve Bayes classifier. Suggested a naive method for identifying hate speech on Twitter. The training set's semantic and emotion characteristics, in addition to unigrams and pattern features, serve as the foundation for this method. Features on Unigrams assist in identifying any overt hate speech. Pattern traits aid in the recognition of any extended or implied hate speech. While the sentiment feature extracts the tweets' polarity, the semantic feature locates any emphasised expression. These characteristics aid in the construction of a tweet categorization classifier. Using the J48 graft classifier and the Weka toolkit, the classification is completed. taken phrases from a few of the biggest "hate sites" in the US. Semantic and grammatical pattern elements were used to categorise each speech in any of the three classifications: "strongly hateful," "weakly hateful," or "non-hateful." F1 score following the assessment.

3. Proposed Methodology

This endeavor's goal is to categories two tweets at once groups: hateful and non-hateful. The actions that were taken throughout the process are listed below.

3.1 Data

The hate speech Twitter dataset for this project was gathered from github. ID, label, and tweet are the three columns that make up the dataset. There are two subsets within the dataset, the 31900 entries in the training dataset and with 49050 entries in the test dataset, in order to conduct categories. Training data is assigned labels of 0 and 1, where 0 denotes a tweet that is not hateful and 1 denotes a hateful tweet.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

The performance of the model may be lowered by data that contains redundant, unhelpful, missing, or inconsistent information that may not be able to provide improved accuracy. It is a crucial step that must be completed before giving the machine learning model the data. The pre-processing of tweets before to categorization is explained in this section.

Figure 1.1 illustrates the various actions taken during the pre-processing stage. The following preprocessing is done on the dataset:

1. Twitter accounts are deleted since they provided no details on the content of tweets.

2. Special letters, digits, and punctuation are eliminated.
3. Smaller terms with less than four letters, such as pdx, hmm, and oh, are eliminated since they are illogical.
4. Tweets are tokenized into individual words after completing the aforementioned three procedures.
5. The final phase uses the porter stemmer approach to eliminate the word's inflectional forms and reveal the word's root form.

Words are collected, and TFIDF traits are taken out following preprocessing. After that, a logistic regression classifier is employed to create a prediction model based on these characteristics. When classifying tweets into hateful or non-hateful categories, our algorithm has an accuracy of 93.11%.

3.3 Feature Extraction

A collection of attributes that are more valuable than others is crucial for training a machine learning model so that it can make predictions. Feature extraction refers to this particular stage of the feature extraction process. To classify tweets into two groups, we use a machine learning classifier that receives a bunch of phrases including TFIDF characteristics extracted from the messages on Twitter. Using a bag of words technique, characteristics from the corpus are extracted and utilised to model the machine learning algorithm. Each word in a document is referred to as a token, and the representation of text indicates how frequently a word occurs. Every phrase is considered its own document, as well as a glossary of every special phrase used in these papers is made, together with the total number of times each word appears. The word's occurrence in the document—rather than its location—is what the model looks for. It considers that if two documents have comparable content, they must be similar. When classifying tweets, a bag of words feature may be used to identify often occurring terms that predominate in the document, however there's a possibility that the words may lack sufficient information. As a result, we also looked at a different method known as TFIDF, which evaluates a word's significance to a text inside a corpus. Where

The term's frequency of occurrence in the present document is scored using Term Frequency (TF). It is computed as follows:

TF is calculated as the total number of instances of a word (t) in a text divided by the document's total number of terms.

The scoring system for inverse document frequency (IDF) determines how seldom a word appears in the document. It is computed as follows:

IDF is equal to $\log(\text{all papers / documents that include the term "t"})$

$TF - IDF = TF * IDF$

When not every word has the same weight, scores are calculated. Words in a given document that are unique or provide valuable information are highlighted by the scores. As a result, the IDF of a rare phrase is high while the IDF of a frequent term is low.

3.4 Model

In order to categorise tweets as either hateful or not, we take into consideration a logistic regression classifier. Using TFIDF characteristics and a bag of words taken out of the pre-processed record, a training dataset is accustomed to train the model. The model is used to categorise the newly test dataset's unnoticed tweets falling into one of the two groups after it has been trained on the training dataset. Using nominal, ordinal, or continuous independent variables, the machine learning technique

known as binary supervised logistic regression classifier algorithm that forecasts the the amount of an outcome or categorical dependent variable. With the use of the sigmoid function, logistic regression maps the value of the dependent variable falling between 0 and 1. Here is the equation for logistic regression:

$$p = \frac{1}{e^{-(b_0+b_1.q)}}$$

Where

p denotes the dependent and outcome variables

The equation is as follows:

b0 = y-intercept;

b1 = slope;

q = independent variables.

4. Results and Discussion

Using a word bag and the TFIDF method to extract features, the suggested model is constructed on top of a publicly accessible Twitter dataset. Attempts were made to visualise the tweets for improved comprehension prior to deriving characteristics from them. Word clouds, in which the larger words are the most common and the smaller ones appear less frequently, were employed to plot hate and non-hate tweets independently. Comprehending the frequency of harmful or hateful words is beneficial. We attempted to comprehend the significance of hash tags in order to gain a deeper comprehension of the hateful tweets. Hash tags are used to indicate the current trends on Twitter at any given time. Thus, we made an effort to determine whether or not these hash tags improve our sentiment analysis work by helping to distinguish between tweets with various sentiments. To do this, we have kept track of all the popular phrases in two different lists: one for racist and hateful tweets and another for non-hateful tweets.

Figure 1.2 Hate tweets

Figure 1.3 Non Hate Tweet

The Twitter trends that are now hateful and non-hateful plotted as a histogram is displayed in Figures 2 and 3. On Twitter, unpleasant themes that are trending pique our curiosity. In order to make it easier for us to identify the precise phrases that contributes to hate speech and aid in the identification of such tweets.

5. Conclusion

In this research, we suggested a system of machine learning that uses the TFIDF technique together with a bag of terms to automatically detect hate tweets. The tweets were classified into any of the two groups using a classifier for logistic regression. We set aside 20% of the dataset data for training purposes. The accuracy we acquired with the bag of words feature was 93.11%, while the TFIDF feature yielded an accuracy of 93.62%. Nearly the same precision is provided by both features. Although the model's performance is adequate, it may perform more accurately by combining language characteristics and employing other classifiers.

References

[1] J.M. Soler, F. Cuartero, and M. Roblizo, "Twitter As A Tool For Predicting Electronics Results," 2012 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks and Mining, 2012.

[2] S. Homoceanu, M. Loster, C. Lofi, and W.-T. Balke, "Will I Like It? Providing Product Overviews Based on Opinion Excerpts," 2011 IEEE 13th Conference on Commerce and Enterprise Computing, 2011.

[3] Hodeghatta, Umesh Rao. "Sentiment Analysis of Hollywood Movies on Twitter." Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining - ASONAM 13, 2013.

[4] Watanabe, Hajime, et al. "Hate Speech on Twitter: A Pragmatic Approach to Collect Hateful and Offensive Expressions and Perform Hate Speech Detection." IEEE Access, vol. 6, 2018, pp. 13825–13835.

[5] Davidson Thomas, et al. "Automated Hate Speech Detection and The problem of Offensive Language." ICWSM, 2017, pp.512-515.

[6] Nobata, Chikashi, et al. "Abusive Language Detection in Online User Content." Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on World Wide Web - WWW 16, 2016.

- [7] Hinduja, Sameer, and Justin W. Patchin. "Bullying, Cyberbullying and Suicide." Archives of Suicide Research Cyberbullying and Suicide." Archives of Suicide Reseach, vol. 14, no. 3, 2010, pp.206- 221.
- [8] Steven Bird, Ewan Klein, Edward Loper, 2009, "Natural Language Processing with Python," O'Reilly Media, Inc
- [9] Han, Jiawei, and Micheline Kamber. 2001. "Data mining: concepts and techniques," San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers
- [10] Gitari, Njagi Dennis, et al. "A Lexicon-Based Approach for Hate Speech Detection." International Journal of Multimedia and Ubiquitous Engineering, vol. 10, no. 4, 2015, pp. 215–230.
- [11] Gaydhani Aditya, et al." Detecting hate speech and offensive language on twitter using machine learning: An N-gram and TFIDF based approach." arXiv preprint arXiv:1809.08651.
- [12] Hinduja, Sameer, and Justin W. Patchin. "Bullying, Cyberbullying and Suicide." Archives of Suicide Research Cyberbullying and Suicide." Archives of Suicide Reseach, vol. 14, no. 3, 2010, pp.206- 221.